

Questionnaire

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements?*(1/1)

Strongly disagree In disagreement Neutral OK Strongly agree

I am convinced of the policy options I chose in both situations.

I believe this study provided sufficient information to be able to give advice to the government.

This is a good way to involve citizens in the choices the government must make regarding school reopening and health measures.

If the government involves citizens on a large scale in school reopening policies through this research, I would support the final decision.

I think this is a method that should be used more often by the Government.

Following →

Questionnaire

How do you think the government should weigh the advice given by citizens in this study against the advice of scientists and experts?

* (1/4)

- The government must follow the advice of citizens
- The government should give more value to the advice of citizens than to that of scientists
- The government must give equal value to the advice of citizens and the advice of scientists.
- The government should give more value to the advice of scientists than to the advice of citizens
- The government must follow the advice of scientists

What comment(s) do you have on this study?* (2/4)

How do you think this study could be improved? (3/4)

What other topics do you think this method should be used for?* (4/4)

Following →